

Envisioning the Future of the World in the Post-Cold War Era

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Abstract: Written by Jenny Andersson, “*The Future of the World: Futurology, Futurists, and the Struggle for the Post-Cold War Imagination*” is a historical record of futures research. It explains that the study of the future has components composed of different claims about how to know and change the future, and consequently, the world. The book relies heavily on the thoughts of futurist thinkers, philosophers, historians, economists, and sociologists who envisioned alternative futures after the Second World War. It revolves around two keywords: the future, and the Cold War. Although the book uses the word “prediction” instead of “foresight,” it is useful to readers interested in knowing more about the historical origins of contemporary futures research.

Keywords: Cold War; foresight; future; futures studies; futurist

The book’s author, Dr. Andersson is a research professor at du Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS) in France. She joined the CNRS and Sciences Po after several visiting and post-doctoral fellowships at the European University Institute, Florence, and at the Center for European Studies, Harvard University. She holds a Ph.D. in Economic History from Uppsala University.

Inspired by her studies in history and contemporary futurist thought, Andersson (2018) has written this book.¹ In the first chapter, she reviewed the hope for better futures that emerged at the end of the Second World War. She has also taken a look at the initial attempts that were made by thinkers and philosophers to the study of the future after 1945. She has inspected the origins of futures expertise and the methodological approaches in the study of the future at the opening of the book.

In the second chapter, Andersson presents a historical argument about the way that historians have dealt with the future and proposes that historians need to reengage with the future. She has argued that in the decades following the cultural turn, historians lost sight of the future and turned to constructions of a past dominated by memory, nostalgia, and loss. She has proposed a transnational history of the future, which engages with recent historiography of world temporalities, modernization, and planning.

The third chapter contains Andersson’s review of the emergence of futurism to a range of writings on the human destruction of the nuclear age by intellectuals such as Hannah Arendt, Ossip Flechtheim, and Lewis Mumford immediately after the Second World War.

Chapter four is a historical report of the Congress for Cultural Freedom (CCF) and proposes that the spread of futurology by the CCF, the Ford Foundation, and the Futuribles project in Paris was a conscious attempt to create a liberal alternative to the theory of Marxism.

In the fifth chapter, Andersson examines the invention of the idea of the future as the “long term” through experimentations with contemporary forms of prediction at American RAND. She has reported that prediction was understood at RAND in a highly specific way, as a social technology for shaping desirable developments.

Chapter six echoes Andersson’s understanding of the social technologies developed at RAND into a reflection on the American future which took place within the Commission

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for the Year 2000 (CY2000), created in 1964 in the American Academy of Arts and Science under the chairmanship of Daniel Bell.

In the seventh chapter, Andersson turned her argument into the rediscovery of the future in revisionist debates in the socialist bloc before 1968. She has examined the role of East European futurists in the transnational networks of future research. She has explained that East European futurists were important in reintroducing the idea that futures were human constructs and central to forms of protest and resistance.

Through the eighth chapter, Andersson has explored the creation of futures studies as a rejection of prediction and protest against the Cold War world order. Taking as its focus the World Futures Studies Federation, she has suggested that futures studies were an example of a kind of neo-utopianism for the Cold War era, which not only claimed that alternative worlds were possible but also tried to construct new ways of envisioning and realizing such worlds.

In the ninth chapter, Andersson has explained how futurism changed in the 1980s and 1990s. She writes, "Paradoxically, in their desire to create new images of the future capable of providing exits from the status quo of the Cold War world, futurists reinvented the technologies of prediction that they had initially rejected and made them the basis of a new activity of paid futures advice and consultancy" (p. 13).

Finally, in chapter 10, Andersson inspected the works of leading futurists such as Herman Kahn and other thinkers like Frank Knight, John Williams, Barbara Adam, Hans Jonas, and many others to see how influential their thoughts were in the formation of a mind-setting that welcomes thinking about the future.

Andersson has been affected by a dystopian image of the future more than a utopian one. Referring to the content of her book, She writes, "In many ways, the narrative of the chapters is more a gloomy account than a hopeful one, because it has more than anything emphasized the enduring role of forms of future knowledge as part of what contemporary sociologists refer to as a 'management of expectation,' in other words, prediction as a form of power over time" (p. 216).

It seems that Andersson has been impressed by the historical records of the Cold War era and its social implications more than the futurists' and futures researchers' works. Her frequent use of the word "prediction" instead of "foresight" indicates her understanding of futures research as an assumptive field of study rather than an established academic discipline. Futures research attempts to shape the future, not to predict it. Forecasting the implications of decisions through time is not paradoxical to the goal of futures studies.

Generally, *The Future of the World* is a genealogical argument about the capacities of contemporary futurist thought and its incapacities in thinking, imagining, and predicting the future. It indicates the period after 1945, especially in Europe shaped by the turmoil of the Second World War. There was a radical uncertainty concerning the future, illustrated by the assumptions of authors such as Hannah Arendt and Walter Benjamin.

Looking at futures studies through the lens of the Cold War, the author concludes that the techniques of the future associated with a liberal conception, such as "prospective" and "futurology", stand out from those associated with a socialist conception, such as "planning." Given the multidisciplinary nature of the field and divergent assumptions, this book presents a coherent overall vision. It re-inscribes the different conceptions of the future and the schools of anticipation in their historical contexts.

Reference

- 1 Jenny Andersson, *The Future of the World: Futurology, Futurists, and the Struggle for the Post-Cold War Imagination* (Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press, 2018).